

URBNANCE

Data Management Plan

URBNANCE Project

Leibniz Institute of
Ecological Urban and
Regional Development

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Abstract

In the era of exceeding planetary boundaries and rapid urbanisation, (re-)connecting society and people with nature can be considered a major leverage point for sustainability transformation. Surprisingly, we know little about the human-nature connection in an urban and sustainable context. The project will conduct conceptual and empirical research with a mix of quantitative (e.g., surveys) and qualitative social science methods (e.g., focus groups). This Data Management Plan (DMP) outlines the data handling along the whole data life cycle of the project. It summarises how the research data will be collected, the metadata standards used and how the research output will be published and archived. This DMP provides the guidance to ensure data is handled following the FAIR data principles¹. This DMP is a living document, and changes will be versioned along the project lifetime. The Leibniz-Junior Research Group URBNANCE² (Urban human-nature resonance for sustainability transformation) is funded by the program Leibniz Best Minds³.

General information

Project	URBNANCE - Urban human-nature resonance for sustainability transformation
Creators (ORCID)	Martina Artmann (Coordinator and corresponding author , responsible for WP 1, 2, 6) Philip Harms (PhD student, responsible for WP 3) Susanne Müller (PhD student, responsible for WP 4), Mabel Killinger (PhD student, responsible for WP 5), Stefano Della Chiesa (Data Steward)
Institutions (ROR)	Leibniz Institute of Ecological Urban and Regional Development e.V. (IOER), Dresden, Germany;
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DMP Template	DFG Data Management checklist
Format	pdf
Language	English
License	Open Access: CC-BY- 4.0
DOI	10.5281/zenodo.7031886

¹ <https://www.nature.com/articles/sdata201618>

² <https://urbnance.ioer.info/>

³ <https://www.leibniz-gemeinschaft.de/forschung/leibniz-wettbewerb/leibniz-junior-research-groups/>

1. Data description

The Leibniz-Junior Research Group URBNANCE will collect observational social science data, including qualitative (e.g., focus groups) and quantitative (e.g., standardised surveys). However, due to the exploratory and iterative nature of the research project, to date, it is not yet fully defined which data will be collected and which specific data management best practices will be adopted. This is particularly true for the second half of the project, in which not yet clarified interventions for fostering urban human-nature resonance will be developed, implemented and evaluated. The URBNANCE team of the IOER will collect the data whereby the various team members are responsible for separate work packages (WP) and the data contained within the respective WP (see general information section, contributors). In general, all WPs will be based on social science methods, including the following data types:

Systematic literature review

The systematic literature review will be conducted by applying the “Preferred Reporting Items for Systematic Reviews and Meta-Analyses” (PRISMA) statement, which considers databases of peer-reviewed literature (Scopus, Web of Science). The data will be organised with reference manager software (e.g. Zotero, Citavi) and managed with standard Microsoft software with the following file format (e.g. DOCX, PDF, XLSX, PPTX). The data coding is done with table sheets (e.g. XLSX). The data analysis is done via R (<https://www.r-project.org/>) or similar software to generate descriptive statistics.

Qualitative social science data

Qualitative social science data will be collected through focus groups and interviews. The data will be recorded with an audio recorder and directly transliterated to text documents. Data referring to any person will be anonymised. The file formats will be MP3 and DOCX. The data transcription and analyses will be done with software recognised as a good standard in the respective scientific community, availability in the institute and the researcher’s expertise, such as Amberscript (data transcription) and MAXQDA (data analysis).

Quantitative social science data

Quantitative social science data will be collected through standardised surveys (e.g., online, face-to-face). The data will be recorded in a data table. File formats are CSV and XLSX. The data recording and analyses will be done with software recognised as a good standard in the respective scientific community, availability in the institute and the researcher’s expertise, such as Social Science Survey (data recording), SPSS and R (data analysis).

2. Documentation and Data Quality

With the project focus on social science methods, the metadata will follow the standard for Social Sciences ([international metadata standard DDI](#) and [DDI controlled Vocabularies](#)) adopted by

GESIS⁴. However, depending on the repository where the data will be published, the metadata is adapted to the respective standard (e.g. [DataCite](#)). The detailed data, metadata and documentation will be developed per each WP by the responsible WP-lead and published as a stand-alone output on the [URBNANCE-Zenodo Community](#).

3. Storage and technical backup during the project

The data will be processed on internal servers at the IOER. The IOER institutional IT department will support the storage and backup during the research process. At the IOER, alongside the primary server used directly by the researchers, the backup system follows a 3-3-2 rule: Three copies of the research data, with three different types of storage media and two offline copies (on two different storage types) in a different location. The backup is daily scheduled and allows data to be restored to a previous point in time. The IT service at IOER is responsible for the data backup and restore⁵.

All project data are stored in the IOER server with a standard folder structure, naming convention and readme documentation. Access control to the project folder is managed by IOER IT. The respective work package leader ensures that the access to non-pseudonymised data will be limited to the individual researcher(s) involved in the related study and that audio files and other media will be deleted from digital recorders after the transcription of the data is stored safely. If personal media and related content will be used for public dissemination, consent must be provided. In all questions regarding Data Protection and Privacy, the IOER Data Protection Officer (DPO) will be involved. Following the DFG guidelines, the research data is stored at least for ten years.⁶

4. Legal obligation and framework conditions

The URBNANCE Data Management Plan (DMP) will follow the guidelines for good scientific practices of the Leibniz Institute of Ecological Urban and Regional Development (IOER)⁷ and the guidelines on the Handling of Research Data within the Leibniz Association⁸. Finally, This DMP will provide the necessary guidance and ensure that the data is handled following the FAIR data principles⁹.

Intellectual property generated within the URBNANCE project will be protected through copyrights covering particular publications, databases, presentations, illustrations, photos, and other products not defined yet.

⁴ <https://ddialliance.org/>

⁵ <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5792643>

⁶ https://www.dfg.de/download/pdf/foerderung/grundlagen_dfg_foerderung/forschungsdaten/leitlinien_forschungsdaten.pdf

⁷ <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5959949>

⁸ https://www.leibniz-gemeinschaft.de/fileadmin/user_upload/Bilder_und_Downloads/Forschung/Open_Science/Leitlinie_Forschungsdaten_2018_EN.pdf

⁹ <https://www.nature.com/articles/sdata201618>

The copyright can be granted as:

- individual/joint intellectual property assigned to individuals of the URBNANCE project who are working alone or jointly on a particular project task
- generic intellectual property that can be used by every URBNANCE member, including, for instance, any commonly developed transfer outputs
- publicly available intellectual property, including data or publications made available on the project website without any specific individual/joint intellectual property copyright

Along with the questions of Intellectual Property and the social science data collected, stored and published, a particular focus in the project is set to data anonymisation in compliance with data protection requirements for collecting and processing personal data. Therefore, the URBNANCE team consults the IOER DPO to plan the empirical work and publication. The level of Intellectual Property granted will be regulated by the nature of the data and output generated in agreement among the project members and in the course of the further development of the DMP.

5. Data sharing and long-term retention

It has yet to be agreed upon which social data (interviews and survey data from the stakeholders) will be made publicly available and archived. These aspects are addressed during the following DMP review. However, as a general rule, the overall project data will be made as open as possible as closed as necessary. The identifier standard for publicly available datasets is the Digital Object Identifier (DOI). Depending on the type of social science data produced in the empirical studies, a metadata description document will be wrapped up per sub-work package and published and assigned with a DOI. Furthermore, the data, metadata description, documentation and other relevant research output will be archived, preserved and shared via the public Zenodo repository and linked to the [URBNANCE-Zenodo Community](#). All pertinent research output will be linked and cited within the research articles. The focus of research paper publications is on golden open access. Thus, data and any other research output is licensed whenever possible as Open Access under Creative Commons CC BY 4.0 International.

The URBNANCE team members are the primary users of the project data. This data will be used to generate scientific outputs in research papers and dissemination at conferences and to the public with pertinent data and its comprehensible presentation. Sharing and reusing non-published data with non-project members from academia and non-academia stakeholders is not foreseen. Eventually, the team needs a careful assessment to prove how to deal with external requests. Sharing and reusing confidential data with and by external persons is not permitted.

6. Responsibilities and resources

The URBNANCE team of the IOER is collecting the data whereby the various team members are responsible for separate WPs and the data contained within the respective WP (see general information section, contributors). Developing the DMP best practices and their application is part of the PhD tasks of Mabel Killinger, Philip Harms and Susanne Müller, and of the IOER Data Steward

Stefano Della Chiesa (IOER internal funded) and project manager Martina Artmann. Therefore, there are no additional costs for the FAIR data management. Furthermore, no extra costs are expected for storage and backup during the project execution and will be eventually covered internally by IOER. For open access publications, costs have been considered along the budget planning. Besides, high-quality journals having cooperation agreements with the IOER for publishing free open access are considered.